

The eggs, very light green, are round and laid on the leaves singly or occasionally in rows. A female can lay as many as 224 eggs. Incubation lasts 4 or 5 days. The first and second of five larval instars feed mainly on the epidermis. The third instar begins eating the leaves. About 1 month is required to complete a generation.

The pest has been most severe in the

screenhouse where varieties are being screened for stem-borer resistance. However, it is common on the IRRI farm and can be considered a potentially serious pest.

Any reader with information on a similar pest should write to the Entomology Department, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Brown planthopper in Borneo

D. J. McCrae, entomologist, Department of Agriculture, Brunei, Borneo

Severe hopperburn covered about 0.2 ha in some seed-multiplication plots at a Department of Agriculture rice station in Brunei, Borneo, in early January 1976. All plants in the area were killed. Large numbers of a single species of delphacid

collected from the outbreak area were identified as *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Rice grown at the station receives fortnightly applications (14 kg/ha) of 3% granular carbofuran. Some affected plots had also been sprayed with methamidophos (Tamaron). The outbreak is the first recorded damage to rice by *N. lugens* in Brunei.

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Herbicides for direct-sown upland rice

M. A. Singlachar, rice agronomist, and C. Chandrashekar, research assistant, University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, Mandya Karnataka-571405, India

In 1975 kharif, nine chemicals were tested for weed control in direct-sown upland rice. The chemicals were sprayed

4 days after the direct seeding of the cultivar IET 1444. Mixed weed seeds had been uniformly broadcast at the time of land preparation.

Of the nine herbicides (see table), AC-92553 showed the best control. The trial was conducted under the auspices of the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project.

Grain yield and weed control in direct-sown upland rice, 1975 kharif, Mandya, India.^a

Herbicide	Formulation concn	Application		Weed wt (kg/15-m plot)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
		Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Time ^b		
Butralin	480 g/l	2.0	4 DS	4.0	1225
AC-92553	250 g/l	2.0	4 DS	1.2	3487
Butachlor	600 g/l	2.0	4 DS	5.9	1115
Piperophos + dimethametryn	500 g/l	2.0	4 DS	3.8	1601
Propanil	35%	3.0	18 DARE	3.4	1419
Oxadiazon	25%	1.0	4 DS	2.5	2513
Fluorodifen	30%	2.0	4 DS	2.7	0924
USB 3153	12.5%	2.0	4 DS	3.9	1662
Dinitramine	25%	2.0	4 DS	2.9	2543
Hand weeding	—	twice	20 & 40 DARE	0.6	3176
Hand weeding	—	as and when necessary		0.6	2856
Untreated control	—	—	—	6.9	1009

^aCD (0.05): 990. ^bDS = days after seeding; DARE = days after rice emergence.

soil and crop management

The use of *Azolla pinnata* as a green manure for rice

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Azolla can use atmospheric nitrogen that is fixed by symbiotic blue-green algae. Observations on the use of *Azolla pinnata* in rice culture at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, are encouraging.

The fern multiplies rapidly except during April, May, and June. Phosphorus promotes *Azolla* growth; superphosphate is a superior phosphate source. An inoculum of 0.1 to 0.4 kg/sq m increased to 0.8 to 1.5 kg/sq m of green matter in 8 to 20 days, amounting to 30 to 50 kg N/ha. Furadan (3 kg a.i./ha) effectively controls lepidopterous and dipterous insects, which damage *Azolla* severely. Pot and field experiments showed that incorporation of 8 to 10 t/ha of fresh *Azolla* before transplanting increased rice yield as much as did 30 to 40 kg nitrogen from ammonium sulfate. Inoculation of a field with *Azolla* after rice transplanting, and the incorporation of *Azolla* after its growth stimulated rice growth. However when water level was high, rice plants became entangled in the *Azolla* mat.

Tests of a tiny water fern, *Azolla*, as a source of nitrogen in rice fields, are encouraging. *Azolla* uses nitrogen fixed by the blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*.